

0D Nanocrystals as Light-Driven, Localized Charge-Injection Sources for the Contactless Manipulation of Atomically Thin 2D Materials

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A contactless charge-injection scheme that allows the local and quasi-permanent manipulation of atomically thin 2D materials, such as monolayer (1L-)MoS₂, over spatial extents of several tens of micrometers, is reported. The possibility to precisely position and localize the charge-injection source to the micrometer scale post-fabrication allows the investigation of local unperturbed electronic structure of the 2D material. Thanks to this novel approach, the important impact of sample inhomogeneity on the charge-carrier percolation that occurs over the entire extent of the 2D flake and proliferates up to 40 μm away from the localized charge injection is elucidated. The apparent driving force for carrier relocation is the initial inhomogeneous electronic landscape of the 2D material. These studies demonstrate that local and contactless charge injection with submicrometer precision delivers an alternative route for charge injection and indicates that local 2D material electronic structure can serve as a key element for novel nanoscale device design.

1. Introduction

Two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides (2D TMDCs) have exceptional electronic, optical, mechanical, chemical, and thermal properties.^[1–3] Due to their monolayer nature, their electronic structure and optoelectronic properties are exquisitely sensitive to external stimuli, such as electrostatic interactions with the substrate,^[4] defects,^[5–7] vacancies,^[8] strain,^[9,10] or doping,^[11] providing local variation of their optoelectronic properties.^[4,12] Recently, local manipulation has been positively implemented to design novel device architectures, ranging from energy funnels for solar energy conversion^[10,13,14] to quantum light sources.^[15] At the same time, this sensitivity to the

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local surrounding can dramatically impact their overall optoelectronic response. Fabrication of devices consists of many steps that might introduce structural disorder and chemical impurities (e.g., through the exposure to electron beam, ion-bombardment, high temperatures, or chemical treatments) that can invasively impact and negatively perturb their local structure (e.g., strain) and electronic properties (e.g., defects, interface effects).^[16] It is however extremely important to study materials properties, while keeping their chemical and physical quality unaltered to be able to address some key questions of technological relevance.

Light is an attractive tool to locally modulate the optoelectronic properties of 2D materials in a contactless way. When excited with light, temporary changes to the optoelectronic properties can be achieved that range from localized modification of the conductance and generation of a photocurrent^[17,18] to an excitonic Mott transition^[19,20] to a negative photoconductivity.^[21] Although compelling, these transient changes rely often on photoexcited populations that decay on ultrafast timescales. Alternatively, recent chemical doping schemes utilized molecular adsorbates, photoactive molecules, or graphene quantum dots to inject free carriers into TMDCs when illuminated.^[22–24] However, in these studies, only a very limited number of carriers per molecule (≈ 1) can be injected, which restricts the maximum extent of the photodoping.^[11] Recently, we demonstrated that the implementation of photoexcited Sn-doped In₂O₃ (indium tin oxide [ITO]) nanocrystals (NCs) deposited over 2D TMDCs results in the long-lived charge separation across the 0D–2D interface.^[25] In this process, after photoexcitation beyond the bandgap of ITO in the ultraviolet (UV) spectral range, multiple electrons are stored in one NC of diameter around 10 nm,^[26–29] while the corresponding holes are transferred to the 2D material. In this configuration, in effect, the underlying monolayer MoS₂ serves as a hole collector.^[25] The charge-injection area is given by the micron-sized laser spot and results in carrier-density variations in the 1L-MoS₂ by amounts comparable to electrostatic doping.^[1,25]

Within this work, we exploited this technology as a contactless charge-injection tool driven solely by light.^[25] The key innovation is that charge injection is contactless as it is triggered by photoexcitation of the ITO NCs. This has several advantages: first, invasive fabrication steps for the contacting with often bulky electrodes is avoided. Second, charge injection can be localized anywhere on the flake with micrometer precision (diameter of the focused laser spot $\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$) determined only by the positioning of the laser. Third, injection occurs at one position only, thus, not imposing directionality to the carrier flow as in other electrode configurations. Together, this delivers the opportunity to study the native and undisturbed 2D material properties and charge-carrier diffusion effects without the application of a field, features

that are unique to our technology. In this way, we broaden the set of tools that can be used to investigate and manipulate 2D materials.

To this end, we engineered a hybrid system composed of 1L-MoS₂ covered in a layer of ITO NCs. We observed that in this configuration a single ITO NC can inject >75 holes to the 1L-MoS₂—a charge-transfer capacity that is not attainable with any other photodoping scheme. Analysis of changes in the 1L-MoS₂ photoluminescence (PL) spectra in the surrounding of the localized charge injection reveals that the local optoelectronic inhomogeneity of the 1L-MoS₂ drives the doping phenomena over macroscopic distances. The resulting long-distance charge separation persists over months, making it quasi-permanent. Spatially-dependent measurements show carrier transport and localization occurring on length scales that exceed several tens of micrometers.

This hybrid system presents an effective method to achieve wireless, optically triggered, and locally induced p-type photodoping of 2D TMDC semiconductors, and highlights the role of local inhomogeneity of 1L-MoS₂ on charge relocation and carrier localization. These results raise important questions as to the uniformity of carrier distribution in devices which rely on charge-carrier injection where charge localization might negatively impact device performance. Thus, this work offers a novel way to obtain in-depth understanding of inhomogeneity of devices based on 2D materials, and at the same time, highlights the opportunity of local 2D material manipulation as a step toward novel nanoscale device design.

2. Photo-Induced Electron Extraction from MoS₂

Figure 1 shows the NC–TMDC hybrid system constructed and studied here. It is composed of ITO NCs deposited on top of 1L-MoS₂ grown by Chemical Vapour Deposition (Figure 1b). The hybrid structure was prepared by spin coating a concentrated solution of the NCs on the 1L-MoS₂ flakes and then by depositing a thin polymer protection layer (≈ 50 – 100 nm). The ITO NCs are composed of a Sn-doped In₂O₃ core surrounded by a shell layer of undoped In₂O₃.^[30–32] This shell passivates surface traps and inactive dopants at the NC surface and additionally aims to create a favorable heterostructure band alignment that reduces electron–hole recombination by promoting hole transfer to the surface, while localizing electrons to the core.^[25] NC synthesis and characterization are provided in the Experimental Section.

Figure 1c shows the PL spectrum of the 1L-MoS₂ before and after exciting the hybrid system with UV excitation (see the Experimental Section). The optical response of a 1L-MoS₂ flake at a single focused laser spot with excitation energy of 2.48 eV (below the bandgap of the NCs) was recorded prior to UV excitation (top panel of Figure 1c). After the light-driven charge-injection process was triggered with UV light for several minutes (bottom panel in Figure 1c), a blue shift and increase in intensity is observed. Comparing the two spectra, it is clear that the PL spectrum not only increases in intensity and shifts in energy but also changes lineshape. The PL spectra of 1L-MoS₂ can be deconvoluted into emission bands from two states, which we assign to a low-energy trion and high-energy neutral exciton (blue and green curves Figure 1c).^[1,11,24,33]

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Figure 1. Illustration of the hybrid 1L-MoS₂/ITO NC structure. a) After photodoping, electrons accumulate in the ITO NCs, while holes are injected into the 1L-MoS₂ and diffuse away from the localized charge injection (not to scale). b) Energetic diagram illustrating the charge transfer from the ITO/In₂O₃ core/shell NCs to the 1L-MoS₂ after light absorption together with a typical scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image (scale bar = 1 μm) of the ITO NC film covering a 1L-MoS₂ flake. c) Variation of PL, measured at the same spatial position, of 1L-MoS₂ before (top panel) and after (bottom panel) photo-induced charge injection. The initial PL spectrum of the 1L-MoS₂ with an excitation energy $E_{exc} = 2.48$ eV (no ITO excitation) is given in red. After photo-induced charge injection with UV light beyond the bandgap of the ITO NCs, the PL displays a blue shift to higher energies. The fit to the PL spectrum (black curve) is given by the sum of two Voigt line shapes, which are assigned to the exciton (blue curves) and trion (green curves) emission. The black dashed lines denote the spectral median, which captures the change in shape and energy of the emission spectrum.

We observe a significant contribution of trion PL before photodoping, which is indicative of an initially high density of free carriers in the 1L-MoS₂.^[1,33,34] As-prepared 1L-MoS₂ is typically reported to be n-doped,^[1,35] so the trions are composed of a neutral exciton bound to an additional electron. After the charge-injection process, the relative spectral weight of the trion is decreased and the exciton contribution dominates. This reduction of trions results in an overall PL intensity increase, as the quantum yield of neutral exciton emission is higher than that for trions, thus increasing the overall PL efficiency of the 1L-MoS₂.^[1,33] These changes in the emission spectrum, which do not occur for UV excitation of the 1L-MoS₂ alone (Figure S1, Supporting Information), indicate that the UV excitation indeed results in the removal of free electrons from the 1L-MoS₂, likely through a photo-induced p-doping due to a hole transfer from the ITO NCs as sketched in Figure 1a,b and explained in detail by Kriegel et al.^[25]

3. Spatial Effect of Photo-Induced Carrier Injection

Next, we consider the spatial diffusion of photo-injected holes away from the localized injection spot. To this end, we track changes in the shape of the emission spectrum using

hyperspectral micro-PL mapping to generate spatially resolved images plotting the spectral median of the local PL spectrum. The spectral median is defined as the energy that divides the spectrum into equal amounts of high and low-energy emission, therefore capturing both peak shifts and changes in lineshape and is used to help visualize the spatial dependence and propagation of the photodoping process. In many cases, we found that spatially localized photo-induced carrier injection from ITO NCs to the 1L-MoS₂ decreases the carrier density in 1L-MoS₂ in regions that are several micrometers away from the photoexcited region and thus not directly illuminated.

Figure 2 provides one such example. Prior to the photodoping process, local PL spectra were recorded (i.e., mapped) over the entire extent of the flake (Figure 2a). We used 2.48 eV excitation (which is below the bandgap of the ITO NCs) to avoid triggering the photodoping process and only excite the underlying MoS₂. As observed in multiple previous studies,^[4,6,8,9,12,36,37] the PL of the MoS₂ is spatially inhomogeneous. Here, we define a border between an edge region and an interior region by the contour (black line, Figure 2a,b,d) that traces the midpoint of the range of emission energies (i.e., a spectral median of 1.809 eV in the original PL map). Before the photodoping process, the edge region exhibits a red-shifted PL emission compared with the interior region, which may be attributed not only to an initially higher carrier density in the edge region but also locally increased strain

Figure 2. Spatial effect of photo-induced carrier extraction in a hybrid NC/MoS₂ flake. Variation in the spectral median of the PL over a 1L-MoS₂/ITO NC hybrid flake a) before and b) after exposure to a focused UV laser spot for 5 min at the location marked with a star. Substantial differences in the spectral median between the edge and core region of the flake (illustrated by black contours in the plots as guide to the eye) are clear already before photodoping. c) Upper panel: histograms of the PL peak position before (red) and after (blue) photodoping. Lower panel: Statistical summary of the difference in spectral median before and after. d) Hyperspectral map of the difference in the spectral median before and after exposure to UV light. The most striking changes are observed toward the edges of the flake with peak shifts reaching 30 meV, whereas the core region remains fairly unchanged.

and/or defect densities.^[8,12,36,38] Following this initial PL mapping of the hybrid NC/MoS₂ flake, a position in the central region (marked by the star symbol in Figure 2a) was locally illuminated with focused UV excitation ($r < 2 \mu\text{m}$) for 5 min to trigger the photodoping process. Figure 2b shows the spatially-dependent PL energy of the 1L-MoS₂ after the localized photodoping at the center of the flake. Again, we used 2.48 eV excitation below the bandgap of the ITO NCs to map the changes and simultaneously avoid re-excitation. Notably, the PL of the entire flake is shifted to higher energies after the photodoping (observed as a color change from yellow/red to blue/green in Figure 2a,b).

Figure 2c summarizes the PL properties as histograms of the spectral median. Before UV photodoping, the initial 2D material flake displays a broad distribution of peak positions centered around 1.81 eV (red histogram). After localized UV exposure, the distribution narrows significantly and centers around 1.83 eV (blue histogram). On average, the photodoping process shifts the emission energy by 17 meV, and the maximum shift reaches values up to 30 meV (green histogram). The spatially-dependent changes in the 1L-MoS₂ PL are summarized by the difference plot in Figure 2d. Although we photoexcited only a localized spot in the center region with UV light, the most dramatic changes in the 1L-MoS₂ PL occur in the edge region. Strikingly, the region where the hybrid NC/MoS₂ system was illuminated with UV excitation at the center exhibits nearly no change in the PL spectrum (see Figure S2, Supporting

Information, for the temporal evolution of the spectra at the center of the flake during photodoping), whereas the biggest changes are observed toward the edges of the flake (c.f. Figure 1c, which is a representative example of the PL variations at the edge of the flake). Furthermore, the intensity of the PL in the edge region increases significantly after localized UV exposure (Figure S2a, Supporting Information). These results indicate that the effect of the photo-induced electron extraction from the MoS₂ flake is not confined to the UV excitation spot of the laser. Importantly, we note that no such changes were observed in the 1L-MoS₂ PL under UV excitation without the NCs (Figure S1, Supporting Information).

In Figure 3a,b, we report histograms of the exciton (upper panel) and trion (lower panel) contribution to the PL spectra, extracted from the deconvolution of the emission bands into trion and exciton emission for each point of the map (see Supporting Information for details on the fitting). Initially, the trion PL contributes to the spectra with a broad distribution of its spectral weight (red histograms), representing the initial inhomogeneity of the flake. After photodoping (blue histograms) the exciton emission is enhanced at the expense of the trion emission, as a result of the photo-induced hole transfer from the ITO NCs to the 1L-MoS₂. We exploited this deconvolution of room temperature PL into its exciton and trion components to estimate the carrier concentrations. This estimation allows us to extract information on the variation of the level of doping in the 1L-MoS₂ from the change in the relative exciton-to-trion

Figure 3. Carrier-density reduction in a MoS₂ monolayer due to UV photodoping. Statistical summary of the spectral contributions of excitons and trions to the PL over the entire hybrid NC/MoS₂, before (in red) and after (in blue) the photodoping. Quasiparticle contributions are calculated by fitting the PL emission with two Voigt line profiles and by separately plotting the spectral weight of the exciton (a, upper panel) and trion (b, lower panel). Illustration of the electron carrier density in the 1L-MoS₂/ITO flake c) before and d) after exposing the hybrid system to UV light. The impact of the photodoping is evident in the sharp reduction of carriers in the 1L-MoS₂ flake, leading to a more smooth spatial distribution of the carrier density. e) Variation in the electron carrier density before (red) and after (blue) the photodoping. The initial broad distribution shifts significantly and narrows to low carrier-density values ($n < 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) due to the injection of photo-holes in the system.

ratio ($I^{\text{exc}}/I^{\text{trion}}$).^[1,11,24,33] By applying the mass action model (see Supporting Information), which describes the equilibrium of excitons (n_x), trions (n_t), and free carriers (n_e) in the system, we calculate the initial electron carrier density of the flake (Figure 3c) and the final carrier density after the photodoping (Figure 3d).^[25] From the comparison between the two carrier-density maps, it is evident that the photodoping of the ITO NCs in the hybrid 1L-MoS₂/ITO system leads to a sharp reduction of the extra carriers in the 1L-MoS₂ flake. Remarkably, the final concentration of charges in the semiconductor is more homogeneous than the initial one, with photodoping, leading to a smoother spatial distribution of the carrier density. Figure 3e reports a histogram of the local carrier density of the system before and after the photodoping, highlighting the shift to low densities ($n < 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) and the associated increase in homogeneity due to the reduction of the initial high carrier density. We extract an average decrease in carrier density of $\approx 2.3 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, which is in the range of carrier-density changes achieved in electrostatically doped MoS₂.^[1,34] with maximum values up to more than $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. To check the long-term stability of the photodoping and carrier diffusion effects, we measured the same hybrid flake before, immediately after, and 38 days after the UV excitation (see Figure S4, Supporting Information). We find that the photo-induced hole doping is quasi-permanent, i.e., stable on a timescale of months as already reported in our previous work.^[25] Notably, we observed comparable photo-induced variations in similar systems in which we varied the position of the illumination spot on the flake (Figure S5, Supporting Information). No significant influence on the carrier-density manipulation was found from the local injection point, but it rather corresponds to the initial level of n-doping in the 2D material flake.

4. Large Spatial Extent of Photo-Induced Hole Injection

To study the maximum spatial extent of the photodoping in the 1L-MoS₂/ITO hybrid structures, we examine the effect in a larger-area ($\approx 40 \times 60 \mu\text{m}^2$) polycrystalline 1L-MoS₂ as shown in Figure 4. This spatially extended system is more representative of a continuous film of 1L-MoS₂ and is composed of multiple 1L-MoS₂ flakes that have merged together to form a network of micron-sized crystalline domains separated by grain boundaries. As mentioned earlier, we recorded the spatially dependent PL spectrum of the 1L-MoS₂ before and after focused UV excitation to trigger the photodoping process (purple star in Figure 4a,b). The difference map of the entire area (Figure 4c) shows that after photodoping, the spectral median of the PL increases by up to 30 meV over impressive distances ($>40 \mu\text{m}$) away from the micrometer-sized excitation spot where the photodoping was performed. Notably, the impact of local UV exposure of this hybrid NC/1L-MoS₂ system is not spatially uniform and the most prevalent effects coincide with the grain boundaries between the individual MoS₂ flakes. The correlation between the initial energy of the 1L-MoS₂ PL emission and the magnitude of the photo-induced blue-shift in the spectral median is shown in Figure S6, Supporting Information, displaying an inverse trend with larger variations observed for regions with lower initial PL energy. To further investigate this correlation, we fitted the entire spectral map to split the PL spectra into its contribution of exciton and trion PL in analogy to what we performed earlier. Strikingly, the highest trion population is located close to grain boundary regions and vanishes after localized UV exposure, as illustrated by the relative increase in PL intensity along the grain boundaries (Figure S3c,d, Supporting Information).

Figure 4. Spatial extent of photo-induced electron extraction: tens of micrometers in distance and preferentially along grain boundaries. Spectral median of a large area of the 1L-MoS₂/ITO hybrid with multiple connected flakes a) before and b) after the exposure to the UV laser source. Photodoping was performed at the purple-colored star in a micrometer-sized spot. Scale bar = 10 μm. c) Map of the photo-induced variations of the spectral median of the 1L-MoS₂ PL, reaching changes of more than 30 meV. The impact of the photo-injected carriers into the 2D material is not spatially uniform and it is stronger along edges and grain boundaries of the flake. d) Normalized statistical correlation of the magnitude of the change in the initial carrier density (Δ) with the distance from the excitation spot. We note that significant variations reach distances of more than 40 μm, and that the magnitude of Δ is not strongly correlated to the distance from the point where photodoping was conducted. e) Reduction in the carrier density as a function of the initial carrier density of the 1L-MoS₂. The striking one-to-one linear relation: (dashed line for comparison) between the maximum charge density variations induced and initial concentration of extra charges suggests that it is possible to completely undope the monolayer and restore a zero-doping condition in the semiconductor, regardless of the initial carrier concentration or of the distance from the excitation source.

From the fitting of the PL spectra, we again extract the carrier density of the 1L-MoS₂ for each point of the map, and display, in Figure S6a (Supporting Information), the variation of carrier density before and after UV exposure. A statistical representation (normalized counts) of the carrier-density changes versus distance from the excitation spot is shown in Figure 4d. At the extreme, changes in the carrier density on the order of $\approx 1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ are detected more than 40 μm away from where the photodoping was performed. Remarkably, we do not observe a strong correlation between the change in the carrier density (as well as the spectral median) and the distance from the localized charge injection (Figure S7, Supporting Information). This lack of correlation indicates that distance is not the limiting factor for the accumulation of carriers in specific locations of 1L-MoS₂. Figure 4e shows the photo-induced variation in the carrier density as a function of the initial carrier density, highlighting that the maximum reduction of charges is equal to the initial carrier density. Even with such a large area involved, composed of multiple flakes merged together, the striking one-to-one linear relation between the initial carrier concentration and the maximum variation suggests that the 1L-MoS₂ tends to return to the intrinsic doping condition, regardless of the distance from the excitation source. In fact, the photo-injected holes annihilate the extra electrons in the 1L-MoS₂, lowering the carrier density to intrinsic

values ($n < 2 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)^[39–41] in an area of more than 2200 μm² (Figure S6, Supporting Information) with a micrometer-sized excitation spot.

Although in electrostatic devices the current is forced to flow between two electrodes averaging over the volume (for electrical contacts) or the area of the back-gate (in electrostatic gating), here, no field is applied and hence there is no predetermined driving force for the injected carriers. In fact, by avoiding the averaging, it might become possible to establish transport measurements to extract local values of resistivity in real time, going beyond conventional transport measurements. Here, we hypothesize that the driving force of the relocation of the carriers within the single layer is the initial local concentration of extra electrons leading to diffusion currents and annihilation of the local carrier density. Although this explanation consistently describes most of the experimental aspects presented, it does not provide a complete picture of the dynamics of the system. Ideally, we could expect the hybrid system to reach a perfectly uniform distribution of the carrier densities (and spectral medians) after the photodoping, while the final maps still present inhomogeneities. There are several possible contributions to the deviations that we observe. The electronic landscape of single layers is extremely sensitive to local effects, including higher defect density (such as S vacancies) as well as inhomogeneous

strain due to interactions with the underlying substrate.^[8,9,37] Here, Raman spectroscopic imaging (Figure S8, Supporting Information)^[10,13] indicates that the edges and other regions with the largest photo-induced increase in spectral median have lower tensile strain. Strain effects on the band structure of monolayer TMDCs are well-documented,^[9,13,14,37,38] showing that tensile strain relaxation increases the quasiparticle energies for electrons and holes at the K point.^[13] In our case, such an increase in the valence band energy would provide a driving force to reequilibrate electrons from the edges and grain boundaries as electrons are extracted from the center of the flake due to the localized photodoping.^[10] However, the extent of the PL changes observed by us after photo-excitation are larger than the spatial variation of the strain, suggesting that the electronic structure in monolayer TMDC flakes varies more gradually toward the center of the flakes than observed in the strain (Figure S8, Supporting Information). Moreover, we have to consider the possibility that the photodoping process was not complete and hence not enough photo-holes were injected into the monolayer to compensate for all the extra electrons naturally present in the material. This would explain the discrepancy observed in the maximum variation in carrier density (Figure 4e) and could represent a limiting factor to the maximum area affected with a given power provided at the excitation spot.

Finally, we give a quantitative estimate of the photo-induced carrier injection into the 1L-MoS₂ from the ITO NCs and the processes involved. As shown in Figure 2–4, delocalized variations in carrier density are observed over the entire flake, favoring the outer regions. Analysis of the exciton/trion spectral weight over the entire area investigated in Figure 4 was applied to those areas where the change in the spectral median was larger than 10 meV. We calculated the total number of transferred charges, which corresponds to 50–100 transferred holes per NC (see Supporting Information for more detail). We highlight here that reaching UV photo-induced charging of optimized NCs can result in up to 250 carriers per NC^[26], and thus that our light-induced charge-injection scheme might be further optimized by overcoming intrinsic limitations of the NCs themselves. Despite having detected carrier-density variations in 1L-MoS₂ only up to the initial natural doping level, we anticipate that further p-type doping can be obtained by choosing optimized materials systems or through an external biasing of the 2D semiconductor.

To summarize, this unique noninvasive photodoping scheme enables us to locally inject charges with submicrometer precision. In this way, we uncover charge relocation and propagation effects in the surrounding 2D material flake undisturbed by the influence of any solid or bulky connections—a feature that is unique to our technology. The advances in this work are made possible by the cooperative electronic properties of the ITO NCs and the monolayer MoS₂. Quasi-permanent changes of the MoS₂ carrier density (by up to $\approx 1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) are obtained through the injection of multiple holes per ITO NC. The effects are observed over surprisingly long distances up to 40 μm away from the local (micron sized) excitation spot, covering an area of thousands of μm^2 . Carrier relocation and accumulation coincides with initially enhanced n-type doping and preferentially along edges and grain boundaries, presumably related to the presence of defects or vacancies. The striking one-to-one relation between the initial carrier density and its maximum variation suggests

that the 1L-MoS₂ tends to reach more uniform doping conditions, regardless of the distance from the excitation source. Our results show that remote light-driven doping is a powerful tool to reduce electronic inhomogeneities and enhance PL emission efficiency in 1L-MoS₂ and highlights an important role of the structural environment of TMDCs. This new tool to locally inject carriers introduces possibilities to remotely manipulate the electronic structure of 2D semiconductors with micrometer precision, and to locally investigate diffusion and transport processes in 2D materials. Furthermore, we foresee that this photodoping process combined with local electronic structure control of TMDCs opens new functionality and application spaces for monolayer TMDC hybrids for energy conversion, exciton funneling, or quantum optics.

5. Experimental Section

ITO NC Synthesis: A standard well-known synthesis was followed for the preparation of ITO/In₂O₃ core/shell NCs.^[36,37] The precursor solution for the doped core was prepared mixing in one vial tin(IV) acetate and indium(III) acetate with a 1:9 Sn:In ratio. Oleic acid was added in a 1:6 metal-to-acid ratio to yield a 10% Sn-doped ITO precursor solution. The precursor solution for the undoped shell was prepared mixing indium(III) acetate with oleic acid in a 1:6 molar ratio. Both vials were left degassing at 150 °C under N₂ for several hours. The ITO NC cores were synthesized by injecting the ITO precursor solution drop by drop (rate = 0.35 mL min⁻¹) via a syringe pump to 13.0 mL of oleyl alcohol at 290 °C. When the synthesis of the ITO cores was completed, a small aliquot was collected for analysis, showing an initial core size of 5.9 nm. Similarly, undoped indium oleate precursor was then injected into the solution with the syringe pump allowing the NCs to grow to a final size of 10.1 nm. NCs were washed with ≈ 12 mL ethanol and centrifuged at 7000 revolutions per minute (rpm) for 10 min, twice.

To characterize the size and the structural features of the NCs, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) were performed. SAXS measurements were conducted at SAXSess (Anton Par, Austria), operating with a Cu K α source at 40 kV and 50 mA and collecting the scattered X-ray intensities with a charge-couple device detector (Roper Scientific, Germany). TEM measurements were performed with a FEI Tecnai Spirit TEM (Hillsboro, OR) operating at 120 kV and using a Ted Pella (Redding, CA) lacey carbon grids supported by a copper mesh.

MoS₂ Sample Preparation: The MoS₂ monolayer film was prepared via powder vaporization technique, as described in similar works.^[25,42] Initially, the chamber was cleaned of contaminations by pumping to base pressure (18 mTorr) for 5 min. Then, 2 mg MoO₃ powder (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.97%) and 200 mg sulfur powder (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.998%) were located in two hot zones in the horizontal furnace (2 in. tube diameter). The carrier gas implemented for the growth was 100 sccm Ar. During the nucleation phase, the MoO₃ and the substrate were heated up to 550 °C for 2 min; the temperature was then decreased to 130 °C for the S powder when the nucleation step was finished. Finally, the temperature in the chamber was set to 725 °C for 15 min, while keeping the powder at 130 °C.^[43–45]

Hybrid Sample Formation: The hybrid was prepared by spin-coating 20 μL of the 10 mg mL⁻¹ NC solution at 2000 rpm for 45 s over the MoS₂ sample. To isolate the system, a thin layer of polymethyl methacrylate was spin-coated on top of the hybrid by depositing 50 μL of a 5 mg mL⁻¹ stock solution for 45 s and 2000 rpm.

Optical Measurements: To collect hyperspectral maps of the PL emission, we used a scanning confocal microscope equipped with a 50 $\times$ 0.6 NA objective and coupled to a 500 nm pulsed laser excitation source (2.48 eV; 80 MHz repetition rate). The emission was collected from the sample through the same objective, filtering the (green or UV) light reflected from the laser with a 600 nm long-pass filter combined with a

532 nm long-pass dichroic mirror. The signal was then dispersed by a spectrometer (Princeton Instruments) and collected by a cooled charge coupled device (CCD) camera (Andor). Hyperspectral imaging was performed by collecting PL spectra in each spatial point of the map, raster-scanning the sample with high-precision piezo stages (Mad City Labs) and collecting the data with a custom-made microscopy software.^[43] For all measurements, the excitation density was kept low enough to stay in the linear regime. Contactless photodoping was performed by focusing a 350 nm (3.54 eV) pulsed laser onto a fixed spot of the sample for few minutes. Raman measurements were conducted with a Raman microscope system (NTMDT), using a CW laser excitation at 532 nm (2.33 eV)—with a power of 500 μ W—focused with a 100 $\times$ 0.6 NA objective. The Raman emission, collected with the same objective, was then detected and analyzed with the Raman spectroscopy system.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords

0D nanocrystals, 2D materials, contactless manipulation, nanocrystal–2D material hybrids, photodoping

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